

THE EFFECT OF JOB RESOURCES ON WORK ENGAGEMENT OF NURSES AT HASANUDDIN UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Job Resources are recognised as a key driver of work engagement and have been linked to the problem of nurse turnover in hospitals. The phenomenon of nurse turnover in hospitals is a serious issue that affects the quality of health services. Work engagement is an important indicator of the extent to which employees feel engaged and committed to their work. We investigated how job resources and its dimensions influence work engagement and its dimensions. The type of research used is quantitative research with a cross sectional design with a sample size of 136 respondents with a sampling technique that is proportional sampling. The results show that there is an influence of 64.3% of job resources variables on work engagement. The dimensions of job resources also have a significant influence on the dimensions of work engagement in the form of vigour, dedication, and absorption. However, in the job resources dimension, only the performance feedback dimension has a significant effect on work engagement and its dimensions. Meanwhile, social support and job autonomy were found to have no significant influence on work engagement. Skill wisdom implies that employees are more likely to find their work challenging, interesting and growth-promoting than work that is routine and lacks the opportunity to use one's full capabilities. The implication of this research is that providing responses or appraisals that promote positive aspects of employee performance is important.

Keywords: Job Resources, Nurses, Performance Feedback, Work Engagement.

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon faced by many hospitals today is how to retain competent Human Resources (HR) because of the phenomenon of high turnover of hospital nurses [1]. In Asian countries, reported nurse turnover rates range from 15% in Indonesia [2] to 25% in South Korea [3]. While among Western countries, examples are 18% in the United States [4] and 20% in the United Kingdom [5].

The phenomenon of nurse turnover in hospitals is a serious challenge because it can affect the quality of health services. An increase in turnover not only results in instability of the nursing team and reduced coordination in providing care, but also a loss of valuable knowledge and experience that can affect the fulfilment of patient needs and increase the risk of medical errors [3]. The risk of medical errors is likely to occur if the competent nurse leaves and is replaced by a nurse who is not competent to provide medical services.

Specifically at Hasanuddin University Hospital, the average Turnover over the last four years is 25% Hasanuddin University Hospital Data 2022, indicating the instability of the nursing workforce within the organisation.

If the Turnover rate of nurses exceeds 10%, it may signal a problem in employee retention, and this study may provide insights to address the problem. An in-depth evaluation of the factors causing Turnover and implementation of retention strategies is crucial for Hasanuddin University Hospital to maintain the stability of the nursing workforce and also to improve the quality of health services.

The high turnover rate at Hasanuddin University Hospital (Unhas) has a serious impact on various aspects of hospital operations. In particular, personnel shortages arising from Turnover can impact on the quality of service to patients.

The process of replacing nurses who leave Hasanuddin University Hospital also requires a significant investment of time and money for the training of new nurses, creating a financial burden that can affect optimal service delivery.

High turnover rates also have the potential to create organisational instability and a less productive work environment at Hasanuddin University Hospital, increasing stress levels and the risk of burnout among remaining staff. In addition, this impact can extend to the reputation of Hasanuddin University Hospital in the eyes of the community, affecting patient confidence in the quality of service provided by the hospital.

In the context of previous research, it has been recognised that high levels of job demands, such as excessive workload or time pressure, can result in increased psychological stress and turnover intention. On the other hand, job resources, such as social support and career development opportunities, can increase work engagement and reduce turnover. Work engagement is an important indicator of the extent to which employees feel engaged and committed to their work.

The positive relationship between work engagement and employee retention has been documented in the literature [6]. The Job demands-Resources (JD-R) model has explained that adequate working conditions with a balance between job demands and job resources can increase the level of work engagement, while conversely, the imbalance can trigger Turnover Intention [7].

The Job demands-Resources (JD-R) model also explains that psychological stress, high turnover intention, and job dissatisfaction are all the result of specific work conditions, namely job demands and job resources [8]. Job demands are the most important predictor of employee burnout, while job resources are the most important predictor of employee engagement [9].

Based on several previous studies, it is found that job demands have a negative effect and job resources have a positive effect on the level of work engagement in companies or hospitals. Therefore, researchers want to know the effect of Job resources and the influence of its dimensions, namely the dimensions of job autonomy, performance feedback, and social support, on the level of work engagement in workers at Hasanuddin University Hospital so that it can be used as a consideration for human resource management at Hasanuddin University Hospital in designing strategies to increase work engagement by providing Job resources which are expected to reduce the level of Turnover Intention.

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used was quantitative research with a cross sectional design. This research was conducted at Hasanuddin University Hospital during November to December 2023. The population in this study was the Human Resources (HR) section of Hasanuddin University Hospital, there were 210 nurses working at Hasanuddin University Hospital. The sample in the study used the Lame show formula to produce a sample size of 136 respondents with a sampling technique that is proportional sampling. The data collection was carried out using a research instrument in the form of a questionnaire that had been tested for validity and reliability, which showed that the questionnaire was valid and reliable so that it could be used. The research questionnaire was taken from the Questionnaire sur les Ressources et Contraintes Professionnelles (QRCP) compiled by Jasmine Lequeurr et al 2013 which has been tested for validity and reliability [10].

The data analysis process and techniques were performed using multiple linear regression equations. Univariate and multivariate analyses were conducted. Univariate analysis analysed the variables descriptively by calculating frequency distribution and proportion to determine the characteristics of the study subjects. Multivariate analysis was used to analyse the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable using linear regression analysis. Multiple linear regression was used to predict the value of the dependent variable based on the values of the independent variables. The results of the assumption test show that the data is normally distributed, linear and free from multicollinearity symptoms, which means that the conditions for conducting multiple linear regression tests have been met. The research variables consist of independent variables, namely job resources and its dimensions (job autonomy, performance feedback, social support), and dependent variables, namely work engagement and its dimensions (vigour, dedication, absorption).

RESULT

A total of 136 nurses have participated in this study. The nurses who became the research sample observed had different characteristics Table 1 shows the characteristics of respondents who are nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Table 1: Overview of Respondents Based on Characteristics at UNHAS Hospital in 2023

No	Respondent Characteristics	n	%
1	Age		
	20 - 25 years (Late Adolescence)	6	4.4
	26 - 35 years old (Early Adulthood)	110	80.9
	36 - 45 years (Late Adulthood)	20	14.7
	Total	136	100
2	Gender		
	Male	29	21.3
	Female	107	78.7
	Total	136	100
3	Education		
	D3 Nursing	12	8.8
	S1 Nursing	124	91.2
	Total	136	100
4	Length of Service at Current Hospital		

	1 - 5 years	60	44.1
	6 - 10 years	46	33.8
	11 - 15 years	30	22.1
	Total	136	100
5	Length of Service in the Installation		
	1 - 5 years	107	78.7
	6 - 10 years	24	17.6
	11 - 15 years	5	3.7
	Total	136	100
6	Employment Status		
	PNS	15	11.0
	NPT	40	29.4
	NPTT	81	100.0
	Total	136	100

Source: Primary Data

Based on table 1 above, it is known that the characteristics of respondents based on age are mostly in the age group 26-35 years (Early adulthood), namely 110 people (80.9%). The characteristics of respondents based on gender were mostly female respondents, namely 107 people (78.7%). Characteristics of respondents based on the highest level of education are respondents with the latest education S1 Nursing, namely 124 people (91.2%). The characteristics of respondents based on the length of work in the hospital were mostly respondents with a tenure of 1-5 years, namely 60 people (44.1%). As for the characteristics of respondents based on the length of work in the current installation, the most respondents were 1-5 years of service, namely 107 people (78.7%). The characteristics of respondents based on their employment status were mostly respondents as NPTT, namely 81 people (59.6%).

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents' Perceptions of Research Variables at UNHAS Hospital in 2023

Research Variables	Low		High	
	N	%	n	%
Job Resources	4	2,9	132	97,1
Work Engagement	6	4,4	130	95,6
Job Resources Dimension				
Job Autonomy	16	11,8	120	88,2
Performance Feedback	6	4,4	130	95,6
Social Support	0	0	136	0

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows that the job resources variable has a high level of perception with 132 respondents (97.1%), while the low level is only found in 4 respondents (2.9%) from a total of 136 respondents. The level of respondents' perceptions of high work engagement was 130 respondents (95.6%) and a low level of perception was 6 respondents (4.4%).

Meanwhile, in the dimensions of the job resources variable which consists of three dimensions, the dimension with the highest percentage is social support, reaching 100% (136 respondents), while the dimension with the lowest percentage is job autonomy, at 88.2% (120 respondents). Basically, the research results show high perceptions on each variable as well as on the variable dimensions.

Table 3: The Effect of Job Resources Variables on Work Engagement Variables and Their Dimensions at UNHAS Hospital in 2023

Influence Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Sig.	Description
Job Resources →Work Engagement	0,643	0,000	There is an effect of job resources on work engagement
Job Resources →Vigor	0,609	0,000	There is an effect of job resources on the vigour dimension
Job Resources →Dedication	0,577	0,000	There is an effect of job resources on the dedication dimension
Job Resources →Absorption	0,599	0,000	There is an effect of job resources on the absorption dimension

Table 3 shows that the significance value of the job demands variable is 0.010 and 0.000 <0.05, which means that there is an effect of job resources on work engagement. The magnitude of the influence of the variable is determined based on the coefficient beta value. The magnitude of the effect of job resources on work engagement is 0.643 or 64.3%.

Likewise, the effect of job resources on the dimensions of work engagement shows a significance value <0.05, which means that job resources have a significant effect on the three dimensions.

Job resources has the highest influence on the vigour dimension which is 0.609 or 60.9%, then on the absorption dimension which is 0.599 or 59.9% and then the dedication dimension which is 0.577 or 57.7%. The results show that the job resources variable has a major influence on the three dimensions of work engagement.

Table 4: The Effect of Job Resources Dimensions on Work Engagement Variables at UNHAS Hospital in 2023

Influence Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Sig.	Description
Job Autonomy →Work Engagement	0,069	0,340	There is no effect of Job Autonomy on work engagement
Performance Feedback →Work Engagement	0,600	0,000	There is an effect of Performance Feedback on work engagement
Social Support →Work Engagement	0,111	0,130	There is no effect of social support on work engagement

Table 4 shows that the dimensions of job autonomy and social support on work engagement each have a significance value > 0.05 which means that there is no effect of job autonomy and social support on work engagement.

Meanwhile, the performance feedback dimension has a significance value of 0.000 <0.05, which means that there is an influence of the performance feedback dimension on work engagement with an influence of 0.600 or 60%.

This shows that in the dimension of job resources, which has the greatest influence on work engagement is only the performance feedback dimension.

Table 5: The Effect of Job Resources Dimensions on Dimensions of Work Engagement at UNHAS Hospital in 2023

Influence Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Sig.	Description
Job Autonomy → Vigor	0,099	0,193	There is no effect of job autonomy on the vigour dimension
Performance feedback → Vigor	0,557	0,000	There is an effect of performance feedback on the vigour dimension
Social Support → Vigor	0,084	0,273	There is no effect of social support on the vigour dimension
Job Autonomy → Dedication	0,078	0,327	There is no effect of job autonomy on the dedication dimension
Performance feedback → Dedication	0,503	0,000	There is an effect of performance feedback on the dedication dimension
Social Support → Dedication	0,129	0,109	There is no effect of social support on the dedication dimension
Job Autonomy → Absorption	0,019	0,799	There is no effect of job autonomy on the absorption dimension
Performance feedback → Absorption	0,599	0,000	There is an effect of performance feedback on the absorption dimension
Social Support → Absorption	0,098	0,199	There is no effect of social support on the absorption dimension

Table 5 shows that only the performance feedback dimension has an influence on the three dimensions of work engagement, namely vigour, dedication, and absorption. The influence of the performance feedback dimension on the vigour dimension is 0.557 or 55.7%, on the dedication dimension is 0.503 or 50.3% and on the absorption dimension is 0.599 or 59.9%. This shows that the dimension of job resources that has the most influence on the work engagement dimension is the performance feedback dimension.

DISCUSSION

Several studies have also examined the JD-R (Job Demands-Resources) theory on employee work engagement in companies and nurses in hospitals. JD-R (Job Demands-Resources) theory is a theory used to understand the level of work engagement among employees, including in the nursing sector, such as doctors and nurses [11]. The focus of this research is on the effect of job resources on work engagement at Hasanuddin University Hospital. Job resources are considered to have an intrinsic motivational role because they enhance individual learning and development, as well as an extrinsic motivational role because they facilitate the achievement of work goals [12].

Our research shows that job resources have an influence on work engagement and its dimensions. If job resources are more adequate, then employees' work engagement will be higher. This suggests that adequate resources at work can encourage employees to be more active and more engaged in their tasks. The research is in line with research conducted by [13]; [14]; [15]; [16].

The research also shows that job resources have a great influence on each dimension of work engagement, namely vigour, dedication, and absorption.

The vigour dimension involves variables that cause employees to feel energised, motivated, and happy in performing their tasks. The dedication dimension concerns the likelihood of employees to follow and build on their organisation's goals. The absorption dimension involves the likelihood of employees to immerse themselves in their job duties. Our research provides evidence that job resources play an important role in nurses' work engagement, particularly at Hasanuddin University Hospital. Task-related job resources contribute the most to work engagement when measured simultaneously, as skill discretion and job feedback consistently rank among the three most important job resources for work engagement [17]. Job resources are a construct of external resources obtained by an employee and are not restricted as subjectivity/things perceived by the employee [18].

Our research found that of the three dimensions of job resources, only performance feedback has a significant influence on work engagement and its three dimensions. While the other two dimensions, namely job autonomy and social support do not have a significant influence on work engagement and its three dimensions. This shows that performance feedback has an important role in the work engagement of nurses at hasanuddin university hospital. This study is in line with research conducted by [19] and [20] who found that job feedback has the greatest contribution to future work engagement and one of the best job resources for work engagement in many jobs, while job autonomy makes a smaller contribution to work engagement, due to its ranking position.

Meanwhile, the dimensions of social support and job autonomy were found to have no significant influence on nurses' work engagement at hasanuddin university hospital. This is in line with research conducted by Seppala 2020 who found a negative relationship between job autonomy and work engagement so that it does not really increase work engagement [21]. It is further argued that job autonomy can help increase employee work engagement when the initial level of work engagement is high. However, the effect may change depending on the initial level of work engagement. The same thing also happens with the social support dimension, where social support can help strengthen nurses' work engagement when initial work engagement is low [22]. Social support is a resource in the form of trust, support, and good relationships from managers and other staff. This can help strengthen nurses' work engagement.

According to our research, job resources are able to use a variety of skills; have the opportunity to learn new things and be creative at work (discretionary skills); and know the results of one's work activities and the meaning and purpose of one's work in a broader context (performance feedback). These are very attractive qualities in the workplace. Skill discretion implies that employees are more likely to find their work challenging, interesting and growth-promoting than work that is routine and lacks opportunities to use one's abilities to the full. Similarly, performance feedback provides information about one's activities, building a sense of meaningfulness as well as a sense of achievement and competence, all of which are important ingredients for work engagement. It may also be that seeing one's immediate positive contributions at work builds long-term goals, which effectively increases and sustains work engagement. Nurses who are able to make use of job resources, such as social support and performance feedback, are more dedicated to their work and more committed to the organisation, and are less likely to leave the organisation [23].

CONCLUSION

This study investigates the effect of job resources on work engagement. The results show that job resources have a significant effect on work engagement and its dimensions, namely vigour, dedication, and absorption. As for the dimensions of job resources in the form of job autonomy, performance feedback and social support, it shows that only the performance feedback dimension has a significant effect on work engagement and its three dimensions. The implication of this study is that providing responses or assessments that promote positive aspects of employee performance is important to increase nurses' work engagement at Hasanuddin University Hospital. For example, recognition and appreciation of achievements, and constructive feedback that can motivate and increase employee self-creativity, create a work environment that supports and encourages nurses, it is expected to increase nurses' work engagement.

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